

The impact of herbal incense on improving stress and memory impairment induced by repeated social defeat stress model in female mice

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Abstract

Nowadays, stress is becoming increasingly common, especially among those who experience violence and face an increased risk of developing mood disorders. As the need to find effective treatments for anxiety and depression is increasing, the use of herbal medicine is receiving more attention due to its perceived safety and therapeutic benefits. In this study, a social defeat model was developed using female mice to evaluate the anxiety-reducing and memory-improving effects of herbal incense containing agarwood (*Aquilaria crassna*), cinnamon (*Cinnamomum cassia*), and star anise (*Illicium verum*). A socially defeated state was induced on female mice by 10-day exposure to aggressive male mice. Female mice were then treated with herbal incense for 10 days. The treatment groups showed improved time spent in the interaction zone (social interaction test) and open arms (elevated plus maze test) as well as a percentage of novel object recognition, yet a decrease in immobility time (forced swim test). Additionally, treated mice showed reduced plasma corticosterone. These results indicated that herbal incense showed protective effects against stress and memory reduction. This study suggests that herbal incense containing agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise may offer an effective way to treat anxiety-related disorders. Further research is needed to pinpoint the active compounds and understand the mechanisms behind these therapeutic effects.

Keywords

Aquilaria crassna, *Cinnamomum cassia*, herbal incense product, *Illicium verum*, social defeat model, stress

Introduction

Nowadays, stress is becoming increasingly common and sometimes even overlooked, leading to many serious complications (Shah et al. 2021; Manchia et al. 2022; Association

2023). Data from the World Health Organization stated that currently, roughly 280 million people around the world have an anxiety disorder (Metrics and Evaluation 2021). In 2019, one in every eight people, totaling 970 million people in the world, suffered from a mental disorder.

In 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this number rose enormously (Organization 2022). However, differences in gender will result in differences in reactions to stress (Calderón-García et al. 2024; Hodes et al. 2024). According to several research studies, women are found to be more vulnerable to depression than men (Seo et al. 2017; Redondo-Flórez et al. 2020). Moreover, if they become chronically depressed, the effects are found to be much more severe compared to men, with more serious symptoms and complications (Kornstein et al. 2000). When exposed to potential stressors, cortisol levels increase significantly (Dickerson and Kemeny 2004), which had been associated with poorer memory performance among women (Seeman et al. 1997). Violence towards women lately has become a concerning public health problem that requires urgent intervention. However, while depression is more commonly found in women than in men (Organization 2022), most preclinical studies on stress-related disorders were exclusively done on male rodents (Füchsl et al. 2013; Hirano et al. 2015; Daws et al. 2017).

Incense comes in many different forms, such as powders and sticks, with sticks being the most popular type (Kinkele 2023). The use of herbal incense, particularly those made from ingredients like agarwood (*Aquilaria crassna*), along with cinnamon (*Cinnamomum cassia*) and star anise (*Illium verum*), has long been used separately in traditional medicine of several Asian countries due to its purported calming and therapeutic properties. Besides agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise have also been previously found in several studies to effectively improve symptoms of mental disorders and depression (Chouksey et al. 2013; Sohrabi et al. 2017; Farahbakhsh et al. 2019; Shahrajabian et al. 2019). Modern studies are beginning to confirm the anxiolytic and antidepressant effects of incense, indicating that inhalation of these compounds may influence mood and behavior by reducing anxiety-like behaviors and decreasing corticosterone levels—an established biomarker for stress. These findings open up new avenues for considering incense as a complementary therapy for anxiety and depression, particularly in light of the side effects and limitations associated with conventional pharmacological treatments.

Various studies have applied repeated social defeat stress (RSDS) to study the mechanisms of stress in rodents (McLaughlin et al. 2006; McKim et al. 2016; Okamura et al. 2022). However, a crucial limitation in RSDS studies until now is that most of them have been conducted solely on male mice due to the difficulty of triggering attack behaviors towards female mice since aggression towards sexually matured female mice was comparatively scarce and lower than among male mice. In this study, we conducted a female mice model of RSDS through initiating male aggressive behaviors towards female mice via inhalation, a method of administration that has not been sufficiently researched in other mice RSDS models to date.

In pre-clinical research, the RSDS model is commonly used to investigate the behavioral and neurobiological underpinnings of depression and anxiety (Golden et al. 2011; Hammels et al. 2015). This model is especially relevant for

studying mood disorders in vulnerable populations, such as female victims of violence, who are at heightened risk for developing anxiety and depression (Whiteford et al. 2013; Albert 2015). The RSDS model involves exposing a rodent, typically a mouse, to repeated social defeat by an aggressive conspecific, which mimics the chronic social stress often implicated in human mood disorders. This model effectively replicates key features of depression, including social withdrawal, anxiety-like behaviors, and physiological stress responses such as elevated corticosterone levels (Golden et al. 2011; Takahashi et al. 2017).

The combination of incense's demonstrated psychoactive effects and the rigorous, gender-specific nature of the RSDS model provides a solid foundation for pre-clinical investigation. In addition, the practice of burning incense sticks composed of agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise has yet to be examined scientifically. This research may contribute to the identification of novel, more holistic treatments for mood disorders and memory impairment, with potential applications for both genders but particularly for women exposed to chronic stress. Moreover, the use of incense could offer an alternative therapeutic approach that mitigates the side effects of traditional pharmacological treatments, potentially enhancing patient outcomes in the long term.

Materials and methods

Animal

Healthy male Swiss albino mice weighing about 40–50 g with no abnormal symptoms were used for aggressive screening tests. These mice had been mated for at least 3–4 generations and reared separately in small cages (18 cm × 15 cm) with bedding for no more than 2 weeks before testing. One day prior to the screening test, only partially replace the bedding in the mice cage or do not change it at all to maintain the smell.

Swiss albino female mice, 6–8 weeks old, weighing 20 ± 2 g, were stabilized for 7 days before conducting the experiment. They were given adequate food supplemented by the Nha Trang Institute of Vaccines and Biological Medical and water *ad libitum*.

All mice (aggressive male mice and female mice) in the experiments were separated by age and sex under captive conditions in the Pasteur Institute in Ho Chi Minh City before being brought to the laboratory.

All the animal experiments were conducted in the Laboratory Animal House, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City, according to the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals of the IACUC and the Ethical Regulations on the Use of Laboratory Animals of the University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City (Decision 2672/QĐ-DHYD). The protocol of all the experiments was approved by the institutional review board of the University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City (47/2022/HĐ-DHYD).

Herbal incense preparation

The incense product was composed of three main ingredients: agarwood (*Aquilaria crassna*), which was purchased from Van Ngan Import-Export Company Limited; cinnamon (*Cinnamomum cassia*); and star anise (*Illicium verum*), harvested in Thanh Hoa and Lang Son, respectively. The herbs were thoroughly washed, dried, ground, and sieved through a 2-mm mesh before being mixed with excipients and pressed into 7 cm long, 1.5–2 mm diameter sticks.

The chemical components of herbal incense sticks were analyzed by liquid chromatography (Suppl. material: table S1). The ratios of agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise in the incense sticks are 3:1:1, respectively.

Repeated social defeat stress model

Aggressive male mice screening

The experiment involved employing a method known as “olfactory stimulation” to induce aggressive behaviors in the male mice. Firstly, the female mice were exposed to a combination of feces and urine obtained from the male mice. A brush was used to thoroughly apply the mixture to the head, back, tail, and vaginal orifice of the female mice. Then, each female mouse was promptly introduced into the cage of a male mouse.

The objective of this experiment was to observe and document the aggressive behaviors displayed by the male mice towards the female mice to screen for aggressive male mice.

The criteria for the experiments were based on the protocols published by Golden et al. (Golden et al. 2011), where several parameters were recorded within a 180-second timeframe, including the number of attacks, the onset time of the initial attack, and the overall duration of the attack.

If the male mice attacked the female mice more than 20 times in a row, we stopped the test and considered the male mice to be sufficiently aggressive, meeting our predetermined standard. The experiment was conducted on three separate occasions to ensure reliability. Mice demonstrating an average attack time of less than 30% on at least two out of three testing days were excluded from the main experiment, ensuring uniformity. Aggressive mice identified during the screening phase were then used in the main test.

Experimental design

Female mice were randomly divided into 5 groups, each group of 14–16 mice except for the saline group, which consisted of 11 mice:

- Saline group: Female mice were not exposed to violence and drank distilled water (DW) throughout the experiment, without behavioral tests (SI, EPM, FST, NOR, and Y-maze). This group was used only for the determination of corticosterone levels and hematoxylin and eosin staining.

- Control group: Female mice were not exposed to violence, drank DW throughout the experiment, were left alone for 30 minutes in the cage as shown in Fig. 1 every day for 10 days, and underwent behavioral tests (SI, EPM, FST, NOR, and Y-maze) after 10 days.
- Social defeat group: Female mice were exposed to aggressive male mice daily for 10 minutes, starting from the first attack (Takahashi et al. 2017). After 10 minutes, the female mice were given DW and left alone for 30 minutes in the cage as shown in Fig. 1. Then, each female mouse was placed in a cage with a plastic barrier between them and the aggressive male mouse. This process was repeated for 10 consecutive days with different aggressive male mice each day (Golden et al. 2011).
- Fluoxetine group: Female mice were exposed to aggressive male mice daily for 10 minutes, starting from the first attack (Takahashi et al. 2017). After 10 minutes, the female mice were given fluoxetine orally at a dose of 25 mg/kg per day and left alone for 30 minutes in the cage as shown in Fig. 1. Then, the female mice were placed in a cage with a plastic barrier between them and the male mice. This process was repeated for 10 consecutive days with different aggressive male mice each day (Golden et al. 2011).
- Incense group: Female mice were exposed to aggressive male mice daily for 10 minutes, starting from the first attack (Takahashi et al. 2017). After 10 minutes, the female mice were placed in a separate cage as shown in Fig. 1 with medicinal incense for 30 minutes. Then, the female mice were placed in a cage with a plastic barrier between them and the male mice. This process was repeated for 10 consecutive days with different aggressive male mice each day (Golden et al. 2011).

Drug administration

The incense inhalation process involved placing the female mice in a cage with dimensions of 50 × 40 × 28 cm (Fig. 1). The cage was tightly closed, and three air vents with a diameter of 0.5 cm were positioned above the cage. During a 30-minute period, 0.1 g of incense, according to a previous pilot study, was burned in a corner of the cage, yet out of reach of the animal. The mice remained in the cage for the full 30-minute duration, even after the incense had burned out.

For fluoxetine, 10 minutes after being exposed to the aggressive male mice, the female mice received an oral dose of 25 mg/kg fluoxetine per day and were left alone for 30 minutes in a cage (Fig. 1). Then, they were placed in a cage with a plastic barrier between them and the male mice.

After 10 days, the control group, social defeat group, fluoxetine group, and incense group were subjected to behavioral tests including SI, EPM, NOR, Y-maze, and FST. Following the FST test, the mice were anesthetized with CO₂ ice within 90 minutes, and cardiac blood samples were collected to measure corticosterone levels.

Figure 1. Picture of the mice cage used in the incense administration session.

Defensive behaviors

Female mice in the social defeat, fluoxetine, and incense groups were exposed to aggressive male mice daily for 10 consecutive days. During that 10-minute session each day, the female mice were observed to determine whether they expressed any defensive behaviors towards the aggressive male mice. Defensive behaviors involve retreat, freezing, avoidance, and risk assessment, such as stretched-attend postures (Blanchard et al. 2005; Henriques-Alves and Queiroz 2016).

Evaluation criteria:

$$\frac{\text{Number of mice with defensive behaviors}}{\text{Total number of mice}} \times 100\%.$$

Behavioral tests

Social interaction—SI

The social interaction model is an open-field PVC cube measuring 40 × 40 × 40 cm, marked with areas for interaction and corners. A wire-mesh enclosure (10 cm (w) × 10 cm (d) × 10 cm (h)) was placed at one end of the plastic open field. The test was performed on the day following the final defeat session. A female mouse

was introduced into the side of the open field opposite the wire-mesh enclosure, and its exploratory behavior was recorded within 10 minutes. The open field comprised an interaction zone (an 8 cm wide corridor surrounding the wire-mesh enclosure) and two corner zones (two 9 cm × 9 cm areas in the corners of the field opposite the wire-mesh enclosure) where the total time spent by the mice in those zones was recorded. The aggressive mice were completely novel to the defeated female mice (Golden et al. 2011). At the end of each test, both the female and the aggressive male mice were returned to their home cages, and the test apparatus was cleaned with alcohol.

Evaluation criteria: Time in the interaction zone and in the corner zone.

$$\text{Social interaction ratio} = \frac{\text{Time in interaction zone}}{\text{Time not in interaction zone}} \times 100\%.$$

$$\text{Corner Ratio} = \frac{\text{Time in corner}}{\text{Time not in the corner}} \times 100\%.$$

Elevated plus maze—EPM

The protocol was previously described (Walf and Frye 2007). Briefly, the elevated plus maze apparatus was made from black Plexiglas with two open arms (30 cm

× 5 cm × 0.5 cm) and two closed arms (30 cm × 5 cm × 15 cm) perpendicular to each other, connected by a central area (5 cm × 5 cm × 0.5 cm). The whole apparatus was elevated 50 cm above the floor. The exploratory behavior of the female mice was analyzed for a duration of 10 minutes.

Evaluation criteria: The total time spent in the open arm and total time spent in the closed arm were recorded.

Novel object recognition—NOR

The Novel Object Recognition Model is an open box measuring 40 × 40 × 40 cm. The test was performed as previously described (Lueptow 2017).

Evaluation criteria:

$$\text{NOR} = \frac{\text{Total time spent discovering new objects}}{\text{Total time spent discovering both old and new objects}} \times 100\%.$$

Y-maze

The procedure was performed as previously described (Kraeuter et al. 2019; Kim et al. 2023). Briefly, the Y-maze model is made from acrylic and consists of three arms measuring 35 × 10 × 25 cm (length × width × height) joined together at a 120° angle to form an equilateral triangle. Mice were positioned at the end of one arm and allowed to freely explore the maze for 5 minutes. An entry into an arm was determined when the hind paws of the mouse were fully within the arm. Spontaneous alternation behavior was confirmed when consecutive entries into all three arms were recorded.

Evaluation criteria:

$$\text{Spontaneous alternation rate} = \frac{\text{Actual alternation times}}{(\text{Total number of arms mice entered} - 2)} \times 100\%.$$

Forced swim test—FST

The protocol was previously described (Can et al. 2012; Slattery and Cryan 2012). The forced swim test (FST) was conducted to evaluate the coping strategies of animals when exposed to a stressful and inescapable environment. The beaker was filled with tap water at room temperature (25 °C) (Can et al. 2012). The water level was set at a height of 10 cm, preventing the mice from touching the bottom of the beaker with their hind paws or tail or escaping from the beaker. The test lasted for 5 minutes, and once completed, the mice were dried with a towel and placed in a beaker containing rice hulls to prevent hypothermia. Immobility involves the mice floating in the water without struggling while only making minimal movements to maintain their heads above water. The following behaviors were manually recorded and scored: time spent swimming, struggling, and floating.

Evaluation criteria: Immobility time (seconds) in 4 minutes (from minute 2 to the end of minute 5).

Determination of corticosterone levels

At the end of the experiment, the mice were anesthetized with ice CO₂ and had their cardiac blood collected within 90 minutes after FST to determine serum corticosterone levels using the BioMérieux VIDAS® kit. The procedure was carried out in accordance with the manufacturer's protocol.

Brain perfusion

The brain perfusion process was conducted as previously described (Tran et al. 2016; Mai et al. 2019). Briefly, mice were perfused transcardially with 50 mL of ice-cold PBS (10 mL/10 g body weight) followed by 4% paraformaldehyde (20 mL/10 g body weight). Brains were collected and stored in 4% paraformaldehyde overnight. Then, the brains were transferred to a 30% (w/v) sucrose solution.

Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining

Paraffin-embedded brain specimens were prepared using a Tissue-Tek® TEC™ 5 tissue embedding module (Sakura Finetek Japan Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan), and 15 µm sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin according to a standard protocol. Brain histopathology was assessed using an ECLIPSE Ci-E microscope (Nikon Instruments Inc., Tokyo, Japan) by an investigator who was blinded to the experimental treatment groups (Nguyen-Huu et al. 2024; Nguyen et al. 2024). The H&E staining process was carried out in the Cell-Tissue Department, Biomedical Research Center, Pham Ngoc Thach University of Medicine, Ho Chi Minh City.

Data management and statistical analysis

Results were processed using SPSS 20.0 and Microsoft Excel 2016 software. Values were presented as mean ± SEM (standard error of mean). One-way ANOVA with Fisher's LSD post-hoc test was applied for analysis. Differences are significant when $p < 0.05$.

Results

Evaluation of repeated social defeat stress (RSDS) model

Fig. 2A demonstrates the percentage of defensive behaviors in 3 groups of mice. It could be seen that the social defeat group showed an increasing tendency to express defensive behaviors towards aggressive male mice during the 10-day period than the other two groups. As regards the treatment groups, the rate of defensive behaviors of fluoxetine-treated mice was lower than that of their incense-treated counterparts.

As shown in Fig. 2B, the social defeat group had a higher mortality rate than that of the treatment groups. The mice treated with incense and fluoxetine showed relatively equivalent mortality rates of 12.5% and 14.3%, respectively.

Figure 2. Repeated social defeat stress model. **A.** Percentage of defensive behaviors; **B.** Mortality rate; **C.** Body weight. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-16$ per group). **** $P < 0.0001$ vs. control group, # $P < 0.05$ vs. social defeat group.

Fig. 2C illustrates the body weight of 4 groups of mice. After 10 days of experiment, the socially defeated mice exhibited a remarkable decline in body weight in comparison to the control mice ($p < 0.0001$). Both treatment groups using incense and fluoxetine had higher body weight than the social defeat group; however, only the former one showed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Effects of incense sticks on social interaction (SI) test

According to Fig. 3A, both the disease and fluoxetine groups of mice that underwent a social defeat session showed a decline in time spent in the interaction zone in comparison with the control group. By contrast, there was an increase in the interaction time of mice exposed to incense, with the data approximating that of the control group. No statistically significant difference could be seen between the groups.

As seen in Fig. 3B, time spent in the corner zone of the socially defeated mice that remained untreated was considerably longer than the control group ($p < 0.05$). On the contrary, both groups treated with fluoxetine and incense showed a remarkable decrease in time in the corner zone ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$, respectively) when compared to the untreated group. Specifically, fluoxetine seemed to be more effective in reducing time in the corner zone

than incense, though there was no statistically significant difference between these two groups.

Effects of incense sticks on elevated plus maze (EPM) test

Fig. 4A demonstrates the time spent in the closed arms of 4 groups of mice. The untreated group appeared to spend more time in the closed arms than the control group, though the difference was not statistically significant. Interestingly, a similar tendency was observed in the fluoxetine-treated group, with the data being closely equivalent to that of the untreated group. Nonetheless, the group using incense spent a considerably short time in closed arms when compared to the untreated and fluoxetine-treated groups, and the differences were also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

According to Fig. 4B, the time spent in open arms decreased significantly in the socially defeated and untreated mice in comparison with the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, there was a remarkable rise in time spent in the open arms of the group treated with incense when compared to the untreated group ($p < 0.01$). The group using fluoxetine also spent much more time in the open arms than the untreated group. Fluoxetine effectively increased the time mice spent in the open arms to approximately the normal level shown in the control group, although no significant difference was recorded.

Figure 3. Social interaction test. **A.** Interaction ratio; **B.** Corner ratio; **C.** Top-down view of the social interaction apparatus, delineated with zones. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$. Flu = fluoxetine.

Figure 4. The behavior of mice in the EPM was evaluated. **A.** Time (in seconds) spent in closed arms; **B.** Time (in seconds) spent in open arms. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$. Flu = fluoxetine.

Effects of incense sticks on forced swim test (FST)

Fig. 5 demonstrates the immobility time of 4 groups of mice in the forced swim test. The untreated group spent a more significant amount of despair time than the control group when tested ($p < 0.01$). By contrast, two treatment groups using fluoxetine and incense showed an improvement in behaviors of mice, as the immobility time of these two groups was remarkably shorter in comparison with the untreated group ($p < 0.05$). There was no statistically significant difference between the treatment groups.

Effects of incense sticks on the novel object recognition (NOR) test

Fig. 6A illustrates the percentage of novel object recognition in 4 groups of mice. It can be seen that the untreated group spent much less time discovering new objects than the control group ($p < 0.05$). As for the treatment groups, both fluoxetine- and incense-treated groups exhibited a higher percentage of novel object recognition than the untreated group. However, only the incense group showed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$).

According to Fig. 6B, the total time of exploring familiar and new objects of the control and treatment groups appeared to be higher than that of the untreated group. However, no statistically significant difference was observed between these groups.

Effects of incense sticks on the Y-maze test

As shown in Fig. 7, the spontaneous alternation rate in the Y-maze test did not differ significantly between all groups of mice. The social defeat group saw a slight increase in alternation ratio as compared to the control group; however, the difference was not significant.

Figure 5. The immobility time (in seconds) in the forced swim test. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$. Flu = fluoxetine.

Effects of incense sticks on corticosterone

Fig. 8 illustrates the concentrations of corticosterone in five groups of mice. The level of corticosterone in the untreated group was significantly higher than that of the saline group ($p < 0.05$). The control group, which underwent behavioral tests without being socially defeated, had a slightly higher corticosterone level than the saline group. In terms of the treatment groups, groups treated with fluoxetine and incense saw a decrease in corticosterone levels compared to the untreated group, with the former group being only slightly lower with no statistically significant difference. However, there was a considerable drop in corticosterone level in the incense-treated group compared to the untreated group ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 6. Novel object recognition test. **A.** Percentage of novel object recognition; **B.** Total time (in seconds) of familiar object and novel object recognition. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$. Flu = fluoxetine.

Figure 7. Measurement of spontaneous alternation in the Y-maze. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). Flu = fluoxetine.

Figure 8. Level of serum corticosterone in mice. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. and analyzed using ANOVA and Fisher's LSD post-hoc test ($n = 11-14$ per group). * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$. Flu = fluoxetine.

Effects of incense sticks on hippocampus area in mice

Fig. 9 describes the H&E-stained sections of the mice's hippocampus, including the CA1 and CA3 areas. It could be observed that there was no difference in the structure and number of cells in both the CA1 and CA3 regions between all groups of mice.

Discussion

The use of herbal incense has long been recorded, as it was alleged to possess numerous therapeutic properties (Sheridan et al. 2012; Wang et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2021). Several modern research projects are being conducted with a view to validating those purported effects of herbal

incense. As a result, it has been proved to exhibit some pharmacological effects, including anti-inflammatory, stress-relieving, memory- and intelligence-improving functions (Peng et al. 2020; Han et al. 2021; Hashemina and Sho'ouri 2023). Among these potentials, the beneficial effects on the nervous system seem to become the major focus in researching herbal incense. Regarding agarwood, many forms of this medicinal plant have been investigated in previous studies, such as undirect-heated agarwood tablets (Han et al. 2021), essential oil inhalation (Wang et al. 2023), or injection (Wang et al. 2017). However, until now, investigations into the effects of agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise in the form of direct-burning incense sticks, which is a long-established practice in Asian culture, remain limited. Moreover, to date, these three herbs have only been examined separately, and there have yet to be any studies conducted on a combination of them be-

Figure 9. Histomicrographs of the hippocampal CA1 and CA3 regions in mice. Scale bar: 50 μ m. Magnification: 40 \times (A–D), 400 \times (E–L).

ing published. Therefore, our research decided to further evaluate the anxiolytic effects of incense sticks composed of agarwood, star anise, and cinnamon, which are three widely used herbs with renowned medicinal values.

One reason the RSDS model is particularly useful in evaluating potential treatments for depression is its ability to simulate both behavioral and physiological changes observed in human conditions (Golden et al. 2011; Carnevali et al. 2020). In females, who have been under-represented in animal model research historically, this model is especially significant given the gender-specific stress responses and the unique pathways through which anxiety and depression manifest in women (Takahashi et al. 2017). By inducing a socially defeated state in female mice through exposure to male aggression, we are able to create a robust and reproducible model for testing interventions like incense inhalation.

There was an increase in the percentage of defensive behaviors of defeated mice (Fig. 2A). This aligned with other research indicating that RSDS significantly triggered defensive behaviors in mice, including risk assessment, stretched-attend posture, and flight occurrence (Henriques-Alves and Queiroz 2016). These behaviors reflect anxiety- and stress-related conditions in animals, hence confirming that the RSDS model is an

appropriate model for examining stress-related disorders (Henriques-Alves and Queiroz 2016). The incense group showed a decrease in the percentage of defensive behaviors (Fig. 2A), which supported the potential of this treatment to alleviate stress and anxiety.

To the best of our knowledge, the mortality rate is usually not mentioned in previous RSDS research. It was once documented in a study by Beins et al. (Beins et al. 2021), which recorded the mortality rate ranging from 12% to 47% in mice. In our experiment, the RSDS brought about a mortality rate of 21.4% (Fig. 2B), which was in line with the data mentioned above. This may result from the differences in gender or species of mice that were used. Death of mice, however, did not occur during the social defeat session but may rather be attributed to other reasons such as decreasing food intake or cardio-related symptoms (Beins et al. 2021).

The socially defeated mice experienced a remarkable decline in body weight as compared to the control group (Fig. 2C). This is in line with the study of Takahashi et al. (Takahashi et al. 2017), which also recorded a reduction in body weight of female mice subjected to RSDS. As the food supply was properly maintained throughout the experiment, the drop in body weight may be due to changes in the feeding behaviors of mice in response to stress.

The anxiety- and stress-relieving activities of herbal incense were evaluated using several behavioral tests. In the SI test, it was revealed that the incense treatment showed the effect of increasing the time spent in the interaction zone (Fig. 3A), while the time spent in the corner zone was significantly reduced in both fluoxetine and incense groups (Fig. 3B). Fluoxetine, an SSRI, had been reported to reduce social avoidance by directly increasing serotonin levels (Fuller 1996), which helps improve social behaviors (Gellner et al. 2021) and decrease total time spent in the corner, which is an avoidance area. In our model, the interaction ratio in the fluoxetine-treated group did not increase as much as in the incense group. However, fluoxetine was administered for only 10 days. Therefore, its effect on social interaction might take longer to show as previous studies have shown that acute administration of fluoxetine exhibits an anxiogenic-like effect (Belzung et al. 2001; Uz et al. 2004). A study on male adult mice demonstrated that treatment with fluoxetine showed a significant increase in time spent in the interaction zone (Brown et al. 2011). This disparity may be attributed to the differences in gender, species, and methods used in the experiments. A previous study has shown that agarwood exerts anxiolytic and antidepressant effects, which are related to the inhibition of corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) and hyperactivity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis (Wang et al. 2018). While CRF is a 41-amino-acid neuropeptide that is implicated in the pathophysiology of many psychiatric disorders (Sanders and Nemeroff 2016), agarwood significantly decreases the gene expression of CRF and significantly inhibits the gene transcription and protein expression of CRFR in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus (Wang et al. 2018). For cinnamon, similar findings were reported in another study, where the EPM test, SI test, and FST test were also performed (Nguyen et al. 2022). Mice inhaling cinnamon essential oil showed a significant increase in the total time spent in the interaction zone as well as the total contact number (Nguyen et al. 2022). Besides, the main component of star anise, trans-anethole, along with other related compounds, was also found to have an anxiolytic-like effect, which can help reduce anxiety and stress in mice (Miyagawa et al. 2014). Therefore, these influences on neurotransmitters and the HPA axis may have caused more rapid and pronounced effects on social interaction responses.

The amount of time spent in the closed arms of the fluoxetine-treated group is non-significantly equal to that of the untreated group (Fig. 4A). While fluoxetine can improve symptoms related to depressive behaviors, its efficacy on anxiety-related behaviors, such as those assessed in the EPM test, can be inconsistent in models of chronic social defeat stress (Song et al. 2019). One reason is that fluoxetine's mechanism targets serotonin reuptake rather than directly modulating the anxiety-induced hormonal response (Sghendo and Mifsud 2012). Social defeat stress causes changes in the HPA axis and inflammatory markers, leading to persistent anxiety behaviors that fluoxetine alone might not fully mitigate (Qin et al. 2009; Williams and Edwards 2010; Sghendo and Mifsud 2012). In fact,

chronic social stress models have shown that fluoxetine may not adequately address heightened anxiety states, as it does not directly inhibit stress-related hormonal surges or address the metabolic and inflammatory changes induced by chronic stress exposure (Chen et al. 2024). Fluoxetine exhibited a potential effect on alleviating anxiety behaviors as shown by an increase in time in the open arms (Fig. 4B). However, it could not fully recover the time in the open arms equal to the control group. This was in line with the result of Drapier et al. (Drapier et al. 2007). On the other hand, the group treated with incense showed a remarkable drop in the amount of time spent in the closed arms (Fig. 4A) yet a remarkable escalation in the amount of time spent in the open arms (Fig. 4B), indicating a notable stress response and management. The ingredients of incense sticks, like agarwood and cinnamon, have been shown to have anxiolytic properties, promote relaxation, and reduce anxiety behaviors, such as those observed in the EPM test (Alamil et al. 2022; Nguyen et al. 2022). Agarwood oil is composed of various bioactive compounds, such as sesquiterpenes and chromones, which not only influence serotonin but also other neurotransmitter systems involved in stress and anxiety (Alamil et al. 2022). Inhalation of agarwood activates the olfactory system, which is closely linked to areas of the brain associated with emotion and stress regulation (da Costa et al. 2023). This allows agarwood to have a quick and direct impact on reducing stress and anxiety behaviors, as shown by elevated time in the open arms of the EPM (Fig. 4B). In previous studies, cinnamon essential oil has also been proved to exhibit its effect of increasing time in open arms and decreasing time in closed arms (Sohrabi et al. 2017; Nguyen et al. 2022). This may be attributed to the main active component, cinnamaldehyde, which has been confirmed to possess anxiolytic effects on rodents via several mechanisms (Etaee et al. 2019; Nguyen et al. 2022). As for star anise, its anxiolytic activities have been documented in some publications (Chouksey et al. 2013; Miyagawa et al. 2014). As a result, stress responses observed in the incense-treated group showed more promising results in anxiety management.

Regarding the performance in FST, agarwood, a main compound in incense sticks, has been found to have anxiolytic and antidepressant effects, which affect the neurotransmitter systems, leading to a decrease in immobility through a wider regulation of stress response (Wang et al. 2023). From the dose of 5 mg/kg, SSRIs are shown to specifically decrease immobility and promote swimming (Cryan et al. 2005), which is mainly due to their serotonergic mechanisms. Similar findings were previously reported in various studies, including Kunming mice (Wang et al. 2023), Lewis male rats (Berton et al. 1999), and male Wistar rats (Djordjevic et al. 2012). Another study on Kunming mice (Wang et al. 2023) also showed that paroxetine, another SSRI, and agarwood both exhibited a similar antidepressant effect through a relatively equivalent decrease in immobility time. A previous study on the effects of cinnamon bark extract on chronic stress-induced mice also found that cinnamon had a potential influence on lowering the duration of immobil-

ity time, especially at higher doses (Parisa et al. 2020). Antioxidants play a vital role in treating stress-related symptoms since they can neutralize oxidants and prevent the activation of inflammatory cascades. Phenol is a metabolite commonly found in cinnamon, which has the potential to exhibit antioxidant properties (Ghaderi et al. 2018). An *in vivo* study found that cinnamon can reduce oxidative stress and multiple neuronal inflammations (Momtaz et al. 2018). Polyphenols in cinnamon extract may lessen dementia and exhibit neuroprotective potentials via a number of mechanisms (Momtaz et al. 2018). Besides stress, cinnamon has been found to alleviate depressive symptoms, which in turn can also cause a significant decrease in immobility time (Ghaderi et al. 2018; Momtaz et al. 2018).

Novel object recognition tests evaluate declarative memory, particularly focusing on the mice's ability to distinguish between new and previously encountered objects. The repeated social defeat stress (RSDS) model in this study had shown to effectively impair memory in mice, which was likely due to stress and anxiety. Fluoxetine had been found to exhibit an enhancing effect on memory processing (Flood and Cherkin 1987). Active compounds in incense sticks had been found to aid memory consolidation in several previous studies (Modi et al. 2015; Modi et al. 2016; Teymuori et al. 2021). Regarding the NOR test, both the fluoxetine- and incense-treated groups showed a pronounced effect of increasing the percentage of novel object recognition, with the latter being more effective than the former (Fig. 6). Fluoxetine's primary action on serotonin levels may not fully address the underlying changes in the brain caused by chronic stress, particularly within the hippocampus, which is crucial for memory formation and recognition (El Hage et al. 2004; Mineur et al. 2013). Since fluoxetine targets mainly serotonin levels, it does not directly counteract the inflammation. In fact, some studies have observed that fluoxetine does not effectively prevent hippocampal changes caused by chronic stress, which may limit object recognition and memory ability in socially defeated mice (Li et al. 2017). A study using scopolamine-induced memory impairment models found that agarwood significantly improved the recognition index, indicating a better performance in distinguishing between familiar and new objects (Han et al. 2021). Thus, agarwood incense may offer an effective natural approach to managing cognitive deficits related to stress, particularly by enhancing acetylcholine-related pathways, which are not directly targeted by fluoxetine.

As regards the Y-maze test, the RSDS in our research did not successfully impair the spontaneous alternation percentage in this test (Fig. 7). This did not align with another study, which indicated that the social defeat model caused a decrease in alternation ratio in male Sprague-Dawley rats (Tian et al. 2018). It can be attributed to the difference in gender and species that were used. Several research studies indicated that the performance of female mice in the Y-maze test improved in a few minutes as compared to the poor performance of males (Conrad et al. 2003). Moreover, it was stated in another research that

normal female rodents showed lower alternation percentages than the male counterparts, and their performance was barely affected by mild stress (Tucker et al. 2016). Both fluoxetine and incense treatment had yet to exhibit any improvement in the spontaneous alternation (Fig. 7) and hence the corresponding short-term spatial memory.

Mice that were exposed to a chronic social defeat exhibited a significant increase in corticosterone levels (Fig. 8). Similar results were also observed in various research studies (Keeney et al. 2006; Iñiguez et al. 2018). Fluoxetine, however, does not appear to effectively reduce levels of corticosterone, which was also in accordance with another research conducted on rats (Mitic et al. 2013). Regarding the incense-treated group, there is a statistically significant reduction in corticosterone level compared to the untreated group. Corticosterone levels increase noticeably (Dickerson and Kemeny 2004), leading to poorer memory performance among women (Seeman et al. 1997; Qin et al. 2009). It may explain the relation between corticosterone data (Fig. 8) and the percentage of novel object recognition data (Fig. 6). In addition, corticosterone is the main glucocorticoid that is synthesized in rodents by the suprarenal glands in response to stress (Ferrara et al. 2020). In terms of incense sticks, key components in agarwood play a vital role in modulating stress responses. Hence, they can reduce anxiety and alleviate symptoms of depression, which helps regulate the HPA axis, a major driver of stress and corticosterone release in mice. Studies have shown that the use of agarwood can inhibit inflammatory mediators like TNF- α and IL-6, contributing to lower corticosterone levels (Alamil et al. 2022). However, a study conducted on male Wistar rats showed elevated corticosterone levels in the group treated with agarwood (Miraghaee et al. 2011; Karimi et al. 2012). This difference is likely to be attributed to the different duration of the experiment, gender, as well as species.

In addition to the behavioral tests, the anxiolytic effects of incense sticks were also evaluated via brain morphology (Fig. 9). The hippocampal CA1 and CA3 regions play a vital role in memory processes and learning abilities. Repeated stress induced by the RSDS model in mice can affect the structure and function of neurons in the hippocampus. A study has indicated that social defeat stress has a detrimental effect on the integrity of neurons in the CA1 and CA3 areas (Guo et al. 2022). Interestingly, in our research, the socially defeated mice showed no differences in these regions as compared to the saline group. Similarly, both fluoxetine and herbal incense had yet to produce any changes in the mice's hippocampal area, although those treatments showed improvement in learning memory in NOR. It may explain that the RSDS in our research still did not induce any damage in CA1 and CA3 regions in H&E staining. It is in line with the research by Conrad et al. (Conrad et al. 2004), in which chronic stress may cause dendritic retraction in the CA3 region in male but not in female rodents. Moreover, chronic stress might lead to the elevation of oxidative stress, which has been reported to cause the damage in the CA1 and CA3's pyramidal cells (Toma et al. 2017). Interestingly, both MDA level and GSH level in the hippocampus of our study showed no

significant differences (Suppl. material 1: fig. S1, S2); those might explain the unchanged structure of CA1 and CA3 in H&E staining. Therefore, though incense sticks and fluoxetine may have a positive influence on improving memory and learning abilities, their impacts on brain histopathology, especially the hippocampal CA1 and CA3, still remain unclear and need more elucidation.

Conclusion

Our research successfully induced social stress on female mice via the repeated social defeat stress (RSDS) model with a high success rate. In addition, the aggressive behaviors of male mice were induced by olfactory stimulation, which was a non-invasive method as no drug administration was required. This is also the first study conducted on the direct-burning incense stick made from three traditional herbs, including agarwood, cinnamon, and star anise. The anxiolytic effects of herbal incense were evaluated using behavioral tests combined with biochemical analysis and histopathological assessment. The data showed positive outcomes as herbal incense exhibited its capability to improve social interaction and learning abilities as well as mitigate stress and memory impairment. These results suggest the potential of incense sticks as an effective alternative therapy to western medications with minimal toxicity and side effects and offer insights into the mechanisms and an unprecedented method of administration that has yet to be studied of incense sticks.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: All the animal experiments were conducted in the Laboratory Animal House, Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City, according to the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals of the IACUC and the Ethical Regulations on the Use of Laboratory Animals of the University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City (Decision 2672/QĐ-ĐHYD). The protocol of all the experiments was approved by the institutional review board of the University of Medicine and Pharmacy at Ho Chi Minh City (47/2022/HĐ-ĐHYD).

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

M.T.N: Methodology, writing—original draft. N.P.N: Funding acquisition, methodology, data curation. N.T.Q.N: Methodology, investigation. N.P.N.N: Writing—original draft, data curation. L.M.H.N: Writing—original draft, data curation. T.B.N: Methodology, investigation. H.N.M: Writing—review & editing, formal analysis, supervision, resources, project administration.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary methods and results

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